

Repeated treatment with JWH-018 progressively increases motor activity and aggressiveness in male mice: involvement of CB₁ cannabinoid and D₁/D₂ dopaminergic receptors

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ABSTRACT

Rationale: To date, the exposure to Synthetic Cannabinoids (SCs) has been linked to unanticipated psychiatric symptoms such as agitation, psychosis, and aggressive behavior. In line with this, preclinical studies have shown that acute and long-term exposure to these compounds can result in psychostimulant effects that may be related to CB₁-mediated and dopamine-dependent mechanisms.

Objectives: This study focuses on the progressive effects induced by repeated injection of 1-pentyl-3-(1-naphthoyl) indole JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) on the locomotor activity and aggressive behavior in adult male ICR-CD1® mice. Thus, the interaction with the cannabinoid CB₁ receptor-preferring antagonist/inverse agonist AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), the dopamine D_{1/5} receptor antagonist SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.), and the dopamine D_{2/3} receptor antagonist haloperidol (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) have been evaluated. Expression and distribution of D₁ and D₂ receptors and tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) have been also investigated by immunohistochemistry on brain and cerebellar samples to explore potential neuroplastic events.

Results: The repeated treatment with JWH-018 lead to the exacerbation of unanticipated psychomotor agitation, progressively increasing spontaneous locomotion and aggressiveness. Pre-treatment with AM-251 prevents the effects induced by the SC first, third and seventh injection. SCH23390 and haloperidol significantly attenuate and fully prevent the effects induced by JWH-018 seventh injection when pre-administered, respectively, alone and in combination. Behavioral changes observed in JWH-018-treated mice are accompanied by alterations in cortical, hippocampal, striatal and cerebellar D₁, D₂ and TH gene expression levels.

Conclusion: The present results demonstrated that repeated treatment with high dosage of JWH-018 induces psycho-stimulants effects via both CB₁ receptor-mediated and dopamine-dependent mechanisms.

1. Introduction

New Synthetic Cannabinoids (SCs) appears every year and accounted for over the half of New Psychoactive Substances (NPS) reported by the Early Warning System (EWS) in 2022. These compounds are frequently identified as adulterants of herbal material containing natural

cannabinoids, thus posing new regulatory challenges and public health threats (EUDA, 2023). Most of SCs are potent cannabinoid CB₁ and CB₂ receptor agonists, apparently marketed as "legal" alternatives that mimic the effects of the main psychoactive component of *Cannabis sativa* delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) (Luethi and Liechti, 2020). Scientific literature chronicling SCs-related intoxication cases suggests that their adverse effects can be more frequent and severe with respect to

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Abbreviations

NPS	Novel Psychoactive Substances
JWH-018	1-pentyl-3-(1-naphthoyl)indole
AM-251	1-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-5-(4-iodophenyl)-4-methyl-N-(piperidin-1-yl)-1H-pyrazole-3-carboxamide
SCH23390	8-chloro-3-methyl-5-phenyl-1,2,4,5-tetrahydro-3-benzazepin-7-ol
Hal	Haloperidol; 4-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-hydroxypiperidin-1-yl]-1-(4-fluorophenyl)butan-1-one

those induced by cannabis consumption (Alipour et al., 2019; Roque-Bravo et al., 2023). Among the wide assortment of outcomes resulting from SCs consumption (de Oliveira et al., 2023), a notable incidence of unanticipated psychiatric symptoms such as agitation, psychosis (White, 2017; Freund and Banning, 2017; Graddy et al., 2018; Bassir Nia et al., 2019; Andersen and Walsh, 2021), and aggressive behavior (Schwartz et al., 2015; Rojek et al., 2017) have been linked to these substances.

1-pentyl-3-(1-naphthoyl)indole, also known as JWH-018 ($K_i = 5.82 + 0.61$ nM), which is considered as the first Synthetic Cannabinoid (SC) identified in Europe (EUDA, 2017), is a naphthoylindole that retains higher affinity on CB_1 receptors, when compared to THC. In line with this, it provokes a deeper alteration of sensorimotor responses, body temperature, nociceptive reflex, breath rate, and motor activity, with respect to the THC (Ossato et al., 2015; Vigolo et al., 2015). A previous study carried out by Ossato et al. (2017) pointed out the psychostimulant properties of JWH-018. The study showed that SCs stimulate spontaneous locomotor activity in mice and that the effect is prevented by the pretreatment with cannabinoid CB_1 receptor preferring antagonist/reverse agonist AM251, the $D_{1/5}$ receptor antagonist SCH23390 and the $D_{2/3}$ receptor antagonist haloperidol. This behavioral effect was accompanied by a facilitation in striatal dopamine release, as well as an increase in dopamine release in the Nucleus Accumbens. This study demonstrated that the acute psychostimulant effect induced by a low dosage of JWH-018 (0.3 mg/kg) is triggered by CB_1 mediated and dopamine-dependent mechanisms. A more recent study outlined that the exposure to repeated treatment with a high dosage of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg) can result in the manifestation of psychotic-like symptoms accompanied by neuroplasticity at endocannabinoid system and an increase in striatal dopamine levels (Bilel et al., 2023). On this basis, we currently aim at verifying the role of cannabinoid CB_1 receptors in the progression of the *in vivo* psychostimulant effects induced by long-term exposure to JWH-018. Alongside, we focus on evaluating whether the long-term exposure to JWH-018 impacts on the interaction between the endocannabinoid and dopaminergic systems, as already outlined for psychostimulant responses evoked by acute injection of the compound (Ossato et al., 2017).

The present study investigates the progressive effects induced by repeated intraperitoneal (i.p.) injections of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg) on locomotor activity and aggressive behavior in adult male ICR-CD1® mice. The interaction with the cannabinoid CB_1 receptor-preferring antagonist/inverse agonist AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), the dopamine $D_{1/5}$ receptor antagonist SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.), and the dopamine $D_{2/3}$ receptor antagonist haloperidol (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) has been also assessed. Due to their brain localization and acknowledged role in pathways involved in the motor (Özkan et al., 2017; Bonnavein et al., 2024) and social functions (Ferrari et al., 2003; Frau et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023), immunohistochemical evaluations have been performed on brain specimens to assess expression/changes of dopamine D_1 receptor and dopamine D_2 receptor, with the aim of exploring potential neuroplastic events occurring in the central nervous system after exposure to SCs. In particular, these changes have been assessed in specific regions, such as primary motor cortex (M1), hippocampus, and striatum, with the aim of

providing an overview of neuroadaptations potentially involving structures included in the mesocortical and mesolimbic dopaminergic pathways originating from Ventral Tegmental Area (VTA) and substantia nigra, and designated for modulation of movement (Klein et al., 2019) and aggressiveness manifestation (Tielbeek et al., 2018). Specific analysis has been carried out in the cerebellum, given its role in modulating the onset and vigor of movement (Boecker et al., 2008; Panigrahi et al., 2015), but also in setting the tone of aggression (Jackman et al., 2020; Asano et al., 2024). Further, the potential changes in the tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) levels in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) has been evaluated after the repeated exposure to JWH-018, since scientific literature has pointed out altered TH levels after the exposure to amphetamine in the self-administration paradigm (Miller et al., 2022).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals

A total number of 340 male ICR (CD-1®) mice, 3–4 months old, weighing 25–30 gr [ENVIGO Harlan Italy, Italy; bred inside the Laboratory for Preclinical Research (LARP) of University of Ferrara, Italy], were group-housed (5 mice per cage; floor area/animal: 80 cm²; minimum enclosure height: 12 cm) on a 12:12-h light-dark cycle (light on at 6:30 a.m.), at a temperature of 20–22 °C and humidity of 45–55 %. Food (Diet 4RF25 GLP; Mucedola, Settimo Milanese, Milan, Italy) and water were provided *ad libitum*. The experimental protocols were in accordance with the European Communities Council Directive of September 2010 (2010/63/EU) a revision of the Directive 86/609/EEC, and were approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Ferrara and by the Italian Ministry of Health (license n. 223/2021-PR, CBCC2.46. EXT39). The number of animals to be used has been determined according to the potency ($1-\beta = 0.80$), the significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) to be achieved and the magnitude of the effect observed in the specific test (effect size f) using G Power analysis (Cohen, 1988). Moreover, adequate measures were taken to reduce the number of used animals, as well as their pain and discomfort, according to the ARRIVE guidelines.

2.2. Drug preparation and dose selection

JWH-018 was purchased from LGC Standards (LGC Standards s.r.l., Milan, Italy), while AM-251, SCH23390, and haloperidol (Hal) were purchased from Tocris (Tocris, Bristol, United Kingdom). For *in vivo* testing, all compounds were initially dissolved in absolute ethanol (final concentration: 5 % BioUltra; for molecular biology, ≥ 99.8 %; Sigma-Aldrich, Milan, Italy) and Tween 80 (final concentration: 2 %; Sigma-Aldrich, Milan, Italy) and brought to the final volume with saline (0.9 % NaCl; Eurospital, Trieste, Italy). The solution made with ethanol, Tween 80 and saline was used as the vehicle. AM-251 (6 mg/kg), SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg), and Hal (0.05 mg/kg) were administered i.p., at a volume of 4 μ l/g, 20 min before JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.). The dose of JWH-018 was chosen due to its association to acute sensorimotor, physiological and motor alterations (Ossato et al., 2015; Vigolo et al., 2015) and to long-term alterations in dopamine levels (Bilel et al., 2023). Doses of the antagonists were chosen since adequate to fully block the pharmacotoxicological effects induced by the acute injection of the selected dosage of JWH-018 (AM251; Ossato et al., 2015; Vigolo et al., 2015) as well as its acute psychostimulant effects (SCH23390 and Hal; Ossato et al., 2017).

2.3. Experimental design

Separate groups of mice were injected once a day for seven consecutive days with the following treatment regimen: vehicle (0.004 ml/kg, i.p.), JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) + JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), Hal (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.), Hal (0.05

mg/kg, i.p.) + JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg), SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg) + JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), Hal (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) + SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.), Hal (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) + SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.) + JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.). Animals were then assigned to behavioral tests, i.e., open field ($n = 8/\text{group}$) or resident intruder ($n = 20/\text{group}$), or to tissue analyses ($n = 6/\text{group}$). Behavioral tests were carried out at day 1, day 3, and day 7 of JWH-018-, AM-251-, or AM-251+JWH-018-treatment, and at day 7 of treatment with SCH23390, Hal, Hal + SCH23390, SCH23390+JWH-018, Hal + JWH-018, or Hal + SCH23390+JWH-018. For the immunohistochemical study, animals were randomly picked from behavioral tests groups and sacrificed 24 h after the last exposure (at day 8) to evaluate the short-term cumulative effects induced by a repeated exposure to JWH-018 or its vehicle (from day 1 to day 7). CNS tissues were collected and further processed for histological and immunohistochemical analyses to investigate the expression and distribution of dopamine D₁ receptor, dopamine D₂ receptor, and TH, as peculiar markers of dopaminergic pathway (see following paragraph 2.5).

2.4. Behavioral tests

2.4.1. Spontaneous locomotor activity

Spontaneous locomotor activity was measured by using the ANY-maze video tracking system (Ugo Basile, application version 4.99g Beta). As previously reported, the mouse was placed in a squared plastic cage (60 × 60 cm) located in a sound- and light-attenuated room and motor activity was monitored for 240 min (Bilel et al., 2020; Corli et al., 2023). Four mice were monitored at the same time in each experiment. Distance travelled (m) was considered as the measured parameter. Variations of the distance travelled were repeatedly analyzed setting up test intervals of 15 min for a maximum time of observation of 240 min. To avoid olfactory cues, cages were carefully cleaned with a dilute (5 %) ethanol solution and rinsed with water between animal trials. All experiments were performed between 9:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m.

2.4.2. Resident-intruder test

Concerning the study of aggression in animals, the term ‘violence’ has been used to describe escalated, pathological and abnormal forms of aggression characterized by prolonged and frequent attack bites accompanied by kicking of the hind legs and often preceded by tail rattling and aggressive behavior with brief latency. The most salient and noticeable element of aggression in mice is the attack bite, which is typically directed at the back or flanks of the opponent (intruder mice), accompanied by kicking of the hind legs, and often preceded by tail rattling (rapid vibration of the tail) that may reflect a state of high arousal (Takahashi et al., 2012). To investigate the effects of acute and repeated treatment with JWH-018, and its interaction with AM-251, SCH23390 or Hal, on aggression in mice, the resident–intruder test has been carried out on isolated mice. The number of bites has been considered as representative parameter to primarily focus on the aggressiveness of the resident by avoiding the inclusion of factors that depend upon the escape behavior of the intruder mouse (e.g., attack duration) (Kwiatkowski et al., 2021). This specific approach has previously allowed an effective characterization of the effects of psychostimulant molecules on the territorial aggressive behavior in our laboratories (de Oliveira et al., 2023; De Giorgio et al., 2021; Bassir Nia et al., 2019). Animals were divided into groups (one for each treatment) each containing 20 mice. The resident mice (13 weeks old, ~30–35 g) were housed individually (in a 267 × 207 × 140 mm plastic cage) for three weeks before the experiment, while the intruder mice (8 weeks old, ~25–30 g) were housed in group (5 mice/cage). During the entire week before the beginning of the experiment, animals received a training session once a day, that involved placing an intruder mouse in the resident’s home cage for a period of 1 min. Noteworthy, the last training session lasted 5 min, during which the baseline aggressiveness of the resident mice was assessed. On the experimental day, the resident

mice were tested at different time points (15 and 45 min after saline or drugs administration), each lasting 5 min (De-Giorgio et al., 2021; Foti et al., 2021). The average number of bites counted at the different time points (15 and 45 min) was calculated at the end of the experimental session. The test started as an intruder was introduced into the resident’s cage started and lasted 5 min following the first attack. The test terminated if no attack occurred within 5 min. Resident mice that did not fight and intruder mice that fought during the first test were excluded from the study. The number of bites inflicted by resident isolated mice was calculated. As the presence of olfactory cues can strongly influence territoriality, the bedding was cleaned just once a week during both the training and experimental periods. Blinded and trained observers working together in pairs conducted the experiments (De-Giorgio et al., 2021).

2.5. Necropsy, tissue sampling and immunohistochemical analyses

2.5.1. Brain and cerebellum specimens preparation

After mice were euthanized by cervical dislocation, brains were immediately removed as previously described (Corli et al., 2024; De Luca et al., 2023), rinsed in 0.9 % NaCl, fixed by immersion for 48 h at room temperature in 4 % paraformaldehyde in 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and subsequently postfixed in the same fixative solution at 4 °C for 1.5 h. Tissues were then immersed in absolute ethanol for 1 h, followed by acetone, and ultimately embedded in Paraplast X-TRA (Sigma Aldrich, Milan, Italy). Serial sectioning was delicately achieved by manual rotary microtome. Eight micrometre thick sections of brain hemispheres and cerebellar vermis were sliced in coronal and sagittal plane, respectively, collected on silane-coated slides and prepared for histochemical and immunohistochemical evaluation. Firstly, to achieve the punctual neuroanatomical areas identification, a brightfield low-magnification analysis of haematoxylin & eosin (H&E)-stained samples was performed (Corli et al., 2024; Roda et al., 2020), allowing the choice of precise sections of primary motor cortex (M1), hippocampus, striatum, substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and cerebellum, which were further treated for immunohistochemical analysis to estimate assumed neurotoxicity. Five slides (about 20 randomized sections) per animal were analyzed.

2.5.2. Brightfield immunohistochemistry

To assess the expression and distribution of specific molecules, i.e., DRD1, DRD2, and TH, immunohistochemical experiments were performed as previously reported (Roda et al., 2021) using commercial antibodies on murine brain specimens. The immunoreactions were conducted simultaneously on slides from different experimental groups to mitigate potential staining discrepancies arising from minor procedural variations.

Briefly, deparaffinized brain and cerebellar sections from vehicle and JWH-018-treated mice were incubated overnight at room temperature in a dark, humid chamber with selected PBS-diluted primary polyclonal antibodies (Table 1). To visualize the antigen/antibody interaction sites, a biotinylated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody (Table 1) and an avidin biotinylated horseradish peroxidase complex (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) were used, while 3,3'-diaminobenzidine tetrahydrochloride peroxidase substrate (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) served as the chromogen. Nuclear counterstaining was carried out using Carazzi’s Haematoxylin.

Afterward, sections were dehydrated in ethanol, cleared in xylene, and mounted in Eukitt (Kindler, Freiburg, Germany). As negative controls, some sections were incubated to PBS instead of primary antibodies, disclosing a complete lack of immunoreactivity.

2.5.3. Immunohistochemical evaluations

Sections were examined using brightfield microscopy with an Olympus BX51 optical microscope (model BX51TF), and images were captured using an Olympus C4040ZOOM camera (Olympus

Table 1
Primary and secondary antibodies used for immunoreactions.

	Antigen	Immunogen	Manufacturer, Species, Mono-Polyclonal, Cat./Lot.	Dilution
Primary antibodies	Anti-D ₁	Purified antibody raised against dopamine receptor D ₁	Proteintech (Planegg-Martinsried, Germany), Rabbit polyclonal IgG, Cat# 17934-1-AP	1:100
	Anti-D ₂	Purified antibody raised against dopamine receptor D ₂	Proteintech (Planegg-Martinsried, Germany), Rabbit polyclonal IgG, Cat# 55084-1-AP	1:500
	Anti-Tyrosine Hydroxylase	Purified antibody raised against tyrosine hydroxylase	Merck KGaA – Millipore (Darmstadt, Germany) Rabbit polyclonal IgG Cat# AB152	1:100
Secondary Antibodies	Biotinylated goat anti-rabbit IgG	Gamma immunoglobulin	Vector Laboratories (Burlingame, CA, USA), Goat, lot# PK-6101	1:200

Italia S.r.l., Segrate, MI, Italy). For each evaluated marker, five slides (corresponding to approximately 20 randomized sections) per mouse were evaluated. Brain and cerebellar specimens exhibiting different immunolabeling degree were included across all experimental groups. Immunohistochemical labelling extent was assessed using digitized section images, ensuring adequate exposure time to avoid pixel saturation. Densitometric analysis, intended to measure labelling intensity, was performed using Image-J 1.48i software (NIH, Bethesda, MA, USA), as previously described (Gizkova et al., 2021; Corli et al., 2024; De Luca et al., 2023; Roda et al., 2023). Briefly, image colours were initially inverted to render a positive signal lighter against a dark background, thus correlating increased immunopositivity with enhanced optical density (OD) values calculated by the software (expressed as mean light intensity). The mask shape was adjusted based on the spatial distribution, signal localization, and different layers/cell types of cerebral and cerebellar specimens being measured. The labelling intensity was measured as the mean intensity value over the area, with the punctual evaluation of the positivity area ensured using the polygon selection tool. Immunocytochemical intensity (expressed as OD) was evaluated in three randomized images per section (reaching at least 10 measurements per image) from five slides per animal, with the operator blinded to the experimental condition. The labelling was calculated as the mean intensity value over the area for all sections. Additionally, the density of immunopositive cells (immunoreactive cells number per area in mm²) was measured.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data from spontaneous locomotion studies are expressed as absolute values for the total distance travelled (m). Analysis of the motor effect induced by treatments was performed with two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's *post hoc* test for multiple comparisons. Factor 1 (treatment) and Factor 2 (time) have been considered as variation factors in the two-way analysis. Data from the resident–intruder experiments are expressed as the bite change percentage of each animal with respect to its baseline value (i.e., before the saline or tested compounds administration). Mice that after saline or drugs administration developed aggressiveness (number of bites) with a frequency higher than 50 % compared to their baseline aggressive behavior were considered as “high-aggressive” subjects, while mice that showed aggressiveness within ±50 % and lower than 50 % compared to their baseline aggressive behavior were considered, respectively, as “normal-aggressive” and low-aggressive subjects (De-Giorgio et al., 2021). Analysis of the effect induced by treatments on aggressive behavior was performed with one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test for multiple comparisons. Immunohistochemical results were expressed as mean ± SEM. Regarding data conceded the normality tests, namely D'Agostino & Pearson test, Anderson-Darling test, Shapiro-Wilk test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the analysis was conducted using Unpaired *t*-test. Diversely, for non-normally distributed data, the analysis was performed employing Mann-Whitney test. The differences were

considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed by using GraphPad Prism 9.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., CA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation of spontaneous locomotor activity

The total distance travelled tended to decrease in vehicle-, AM-251-, SCH23390- and Hal/SCH23390-treated mice during the 4 h observation (Figs. 1–2), a response that is similar to that observed in naïve (untreated) animals.

JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) reduced the locomotor activity in mice at day 1, and the effect was prevented by pre-treatment with AM251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) [Fig. 1A; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 53.14$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 48.11$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 0.7546$, $p = 0.8776$)]. On the other side, injection of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) increased the locomotor activity of mice at day 3 [Fig. 1B; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 27.47$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 9.958$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 2.167$, $p < 0.0001$)] and D7 [Fig. 1C; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 43.27$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 21.52$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 5.639$, $p < 0.0001$)], and pre-treatment with AM251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) prevented the stimulatory effect provoked by JWH-018. *Post-hoc* comparison using the Bonferroni correction indicated that the total distance travelled by mice after the treatment with AM251 is not different from that travelled by vehicle-treated mice. Otherwise, the total distance travelled by mice after the first, third, and seventh injection of JWH-018 was significantly different from that travelled by vehicle-treated mice. Further, the total distance travelled by mice after co-administration of AM251 and JWH-018 was significantly different from that travelled by JWH-018-treated mice, but not from those travelled by vehicle- and AM251-treated mice.

The JWH-018 induced hypermotility observed at day 7 was further partially attenuated by pre-treatment with either Hal (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) [Fig. 2A; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 39.92$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 18.85$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 4.057$, $p < 0.0001$)] and SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.) [Fig. 2B; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 63.34$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 35.13$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 6.298$, $p < 0.0001$)]. On the other hand, pre-treatment with Hal/SCH2330 combination fully prevented the effect induced by JWH-018 at day 7 [Fig. 2C; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,448} = 80.90$, $p < 0.0001$), time ($F_{15,448} = 23.12$, $p < 0.0001$), and time × treatment interaction ($F_{45,448} = 7.221$, $p < 0.0001$)], restoring basal level of spontaneous locomotor activity. *Post-hoc* comparison using the Bonferroni correction indicated that the total distance travelled by mice after the treatment with Hal and SCH23390 is not different from that travelled by vehicle-treated mice. The total distance travelled by mice after co-administration of Hal + JWH-018 or SCH23390+JWH-018 was significantly different from those travelled by vehicle- and JWH-018-treated

Fig. 1. Effect of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) and AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), alone or in combination, on the total distance (meters) travelled by mice at Day 1, Day 3, and Day 7 of treatment (panels A, B and C, respectively). Data were collected every 15 min over the 240 min test and are expressed as the mean ± SEM of values from 8 mice/group. Two-way ANOVA followed by the Bonferroni's *post hoc* test for multiple comparisons. Significant differences among groups identified by Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows: **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01 and ****p* < 0.001 versus vehicle; #*p* < 0.05, ##*p* < 0.01 and ###*p* < 0.001 versus JWH-018.

Fig. 2. Effect of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) and its interaction with haloperidol (Hal, 0.05 mg/kg, i.p.; panel A), SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.; panel B), and Hal/SCH23390 combination (C) on the total distance (meters) travelled by mice at Day 7 of treatment. Data were collected every 15 min over the 240 min test and are expressed as the mean ± SEM of values from 8 mice/group. Two-way ANOVA followed by the Bonferroni's *post hoc* test for multiple comparisons. Significant differences among groups identified by Bonferroni correction are indicated as follows: **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01 and ****p* < 0.001 versus vehicle; #*p* < 0.05, ##*p* < 0.01 and ###*p* < 0.001 versus JWH-018; *p* < 0.01 and *p* < 0.001 versus Hal, SCH23390, or Hal/SCH23390; *n* = 8/group.

Fig. 3. Effect of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) and its interaction with AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.; panel A), haloperidol (Hal, 0.05 mg/kg, i.p.; panel B), SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.; panel B) and Hal/SCH23390 combination (panel B) on isolated mice in the resident-intruder test. Data are expressed as the percentage of variation of the number of bites given by the treated mouse (i.e., after administration of saline or tested compounds) compared to its basal value. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test for multiple comparisons. **p* < 0.05, ****p* < 0.01 and *****p* < 0.001 versus vehicle; #*p* < 0.05, ##*p* < 0.01 and ###*p* < 0.001 versus JWH-018; *n* = 20/group.

mice as well as from that travelled by mice injected with antagonists (Hal or SCH23390) alone.

3.2. Evaluation of aggressive behavior

Vehicle, AM-251, Hal, SCH23390, and Hal/SCH23390 combination did not modify the aggressive behavior of mice (Fig. 3), these responses being similar to those observed in naïve untreated animals.

Repeated systemic administration of JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) induced a progressive increase of aggressiveness in mice (Fig. 3), up to a ~ 85 % increase in the overall mean bites inflicted by the resident mice at day 7 of treatment. Pre-treatment with AM-251 (6 mg/kg, i.p.), prevented the rise of aggressiveness observed at day 1 [Fig. 4A; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 4.205$, $p = 0.0083$)], day 3 [Fig. 3A; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 5.711$, $p = 0.0014$)], and day 7 [Fig. 3A; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 7.355$, $p = 0.0002$)]. The effect observed at day 7 of JWH-018-treatment was also abolished by pre-treatment with Hal (0.05 mg/kg, i.p.) [Fig. 3B; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 20.95$, $p < 0.0001$)], SCH23390 (0.1 mg/kg, i.p.) [Fig. 3B; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 17.48$, $p < 0.0001$)], and Hal/SCH23390 combination [Fig. 3B; significant effect of treatment ($F_{3,76} = 20.24$, $p < 0.0001$)].

3.3. JWH-018 alters cortical, hippocampal, striatal and cerebellar dopamine D₁ and D₂ receptors, and TH expression levels

All immunohistochemical reactions were conducted on coronal brain sections and sagittal cerebellum sections from both vehicle- and JWH-018-treated male mice (6 mg/kg), focusing on different CNS regions, i. e., primary motor cortex (M1), hippocampus, striatum, cerebellar vermis, and substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc).

3.3.1. Dopamine D₁ receptor evaluation

Concerning dopamine D₁ receptor, a complete lack of immunopositivity was observed in primary motor cortex (M1) and hippocampal areas from both vehicle- and JWH-018-treated mice (Fig. 4, panels a–d and f–i, respectively). In parallel, a widespread D₁ immunopositivity was detected throughout the striatal matrix of animals from both experimental groups (Fig. 4, panels e and j). Furthermore, as regards to cerebellum of both vehicle- and JWH-018-treated mice, a pale immunopositivity was detected in Purkinje cells somata (Fig. 5, panels A–D).

Accordingly, the quantitative analyses documented a highly significant reduction of D₁-immunopositive striatal matrix OD in JWH-018-treated mice, compared to vehicles (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 1252, $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 4A). Similarly, an extremely significant lessening of Purkinje-immunopositive cells OD was measured in JWH-018-treated mice, compared to vehicle group (Unpaired *t*-test: $t = 3.75$, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 5A). Notably, a significant decrease of D₁-immunolabeled Purkinje cell density was observed when comparing JWH-018- and vehicle-treated mice (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 0, $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 5B).

3.3.2. Dopamine D₂ receptor evaluation

A striking dopamine D₂ receptor immunolabeling was detectable in all the CNS regions examined, albeit dissimilar extents were evidenced in the two experimental groups. In particular, intensely D₂-immunopositive cell somata were noticeable in different layers of the primary motor cortex, i.e., external granular layer (EGL), external pyramidal layer (EPL), internal pyramidal layer (IPL), and multiform layer (ML) (Fig. 6, panels a–c and f–h). Similarly, markedly D₂-immunopositive cell somata were observable in distinct hippocampal areas, namely cornu Ammonis (in particular in its portions CA2 and CA3) and dentate gyrus (DG) (Fig. 6, panels d and i), and in the striatum (Fig. 6, panels e and j). Likewise, as regards to cerebellum, somata of Purkinje neurons appeared strongly immunopositive for dopamine D₂ receptor (Fig. 5, panels e–f

Fig. 4. Cerebral D₁-immunostaining pattern in JWH-018 (6 mg/kg)-treated mice. Representative micrographs show dopamine D₁ receptor immunohistochemical expression in different brain areas, i.e., primary motor cortex, hippocampus and striatum, from both vehicle- (a–e) and JWH-018-treated mice (f–j). I–VI: cerebral cortex layers. CA: Cornu Ammonis and its subdivisions: CA1, CA2, CA3 and CA4; DG: Dentate Gyrus. Light microscopy magnification: 100 × (a, d, f and i; scale bars: 200 μm); 400 × (b, c, e, g, h and j; scale bars: 20 μm and 50 μm, for b, c, g, h and e, j, respectively). A: histogram illustrates the quantitative measurement of D₁-immunopositive matrix OD in the striatum of vehicle- (white bars) and JWH018-treated mice (black bars). ** $p < 0.01$. N. of sections: 20/animal.

Fig. 5. JWH-018 (6 mg/kg) effects on cerebellar immunostaining patterns of dopamine D₁, D₂ receptors and TH. Representative micrographs show dopamine D₁, D₂ receptors and TH immunolabelling in both vehicle- (a-b, e-f and i-j, respectively) and JWH-018-treated mice (c-d, g-h and k-l, respectively). Light microscopy magnification: 400 × (a, c, e, f, i and k; scale bars: 50 μm); 600 × (b, d, f, h, j and l; scale bars: 25 μm). Panels A–D: histograms illustrate the quantitative assessment of DRD1 (dopamine D₁ receptor)- and DRD2 (dopamine D₂ receptor)-immunopositive Purkinje neurons OD (A and C, respectively) and density (B and D, respectively), measured in both vehicle-animals (white bars) and JWH018-treated mice (black bars). *p < 0.05 and ***p < 0.001. N. of sections: 20/animal.

and g-h).

In the primary motor cortex (M1), the subsequent quantitative measurements revealed an extremely significant reduction of D₂-immunopositive cells OD after treatment with JWH-018 in all cortical layers, compared to vehicle-treated animals (Unpaired *t*-test: *t* = 8.62, *p* < 0.001 and *t* = 11.0, *p* < 0.001, respectively, for EGL-EPL and IPL-ML) (Fig. 6A). In parallel, a significant reduction of DRD2-immunoreactive

cell density was observed in the EGL- EPL layers of JWH-018-treated mice, compared to vehicles (Unpaired *t*-test: *t* = 3.30, *p* < 0.05). Any difference in D₂-immunopositive cell density was determined in IPL-ML layers when comparing the two experimental groups (Unpaired *t*-test: *t* = 1.22, *p* > 0.05) (Fig. 6B).

In the hippocampus, the quantitative measurement assessed a significant lessening of D₂-immunopositive cells OD in all evaluated areas

Fig. 6. Cerebral D₂-immunostaining pattern in JWH-018 (6 mg/kg)-treated mice. Representative micrographs show dopamine D₂ receptor immunolabeling in selected brain areas, i.e., primary motor cortex, hippocampus and striatum, from both vehicle- (a–e) and JWH-018-treated mice (f–j). I–VI: cerebral cortex layers. CA: Cornu Ammonis and its subdivisions: CA1, CA2, CA3 and CA4; DG: Dentate Gyrus. Light microscopy magnification: 100 × (a, d, f and i; scale bars: 200 μm); 400 × (b, c, e, g, h and j; scale bars: 20 μm and 50 μm, for b, c, g, h and e, j, respectively); 600 × (inserts). Panel A–F: histograms illustrate the quantitative measurement of D₂-immunoreactivity, assessed in terms of both D₂-immunopositive cells OD and density, in the primary motor cortex (A and B, respectively), hippocampus (C and D, respectively) and striatum (E and F, respectively) of vehicle- (white bars) and JWH018-treated mice (black bars). *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01 and ***p < 0.001. N. of sections: 20/animal.

after JWH-018 treatment (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 266, p < 0.01 and M-W U = 58, p < 0.001 for DG and CA2, respectively; Unpaired *t*-test: t = 2.28, p < 0.05 for CA3) (Fig. 6C). Analogously, a significant decrease of D₂-immunolabeled cell density was calculated in DG and CA3 of JWH-018-treated mice, compared to vehicles (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 0, p < 0.05 and M-W U = 0, p < 0.05 for DG and CA3, respectively). Any difference in the D₂-immunopositive cells density was reported in CA2 region comparing the two experimental groups (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 1, p > 0.05) (Fig. 6D).

In the striatum, an extremely significant reduction of D₂-immunoreactivity, assessed in terms of both immunopositive cells OD and density, was underscored in the JWH-018-treated mice compared to vehicles (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 1033, p < 0.001; Unpaired *t*-test: t = 8.19, p < 0.001, for immunopositive cells OD and density, respectively) (Fig. 6, panels E and F).

In the cerebellum, the quantitative analyses showed a significant reduction of D₂-immunopositive Purkinje cells OD in JWH-018-treated mice compared to vehicles (Unpaired *t*-test: t = 13.2, p < 0.001) (Fig. 5C). Conversely, when assessing D₂-immunopositive Purkinje cell density no significant difference was found between JWH-018- and vehicle-treated mice (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 0, p > 0.05) (Fig. 5D).

3.3.3. TH evaluation

An enhancement of TH expression levels was triggered by JWH-018 (6 mg/kg) in specific CNS regions. In fact, no TH-immunoreactivity was detected in the cerebellum (Fig. 5, panels i–l) as well as in the primary motor cortex and hippocampus (Fig. 7, panels a–d and g–j). However, a clear TH immunolabeling was evidenced in the striatum of mice from both experimental groups, mainly localized in the striatal matrix (Fig. 7, panels e and k). Additionally, clusters of neurons, characterized by an intensely TH-immunopositive cytoplasm, were evident in the SNpc of animals from both experimental groups (Fig. 7, panels f and l), with a more striking immunolabelling detectible in JWH-018-treated mice (Fig. 7, panel l).

Concerning the quantitative assessment, only a slight increase of TH-immunopositive cells OD was observed in the striatal matrix of JWH-018-treated mice, compared to vehicles (Unpaired *t*-test: t = 1.54, p > 0.05) (Fig. 7A, panels e and k). Yet, JWH-018 led to an extremely significant augment of TH-immunopositive cells OD in the SNpc (Unpaired *t*-test: t = 24.7, p < 0.001) (Fig. 7B, panels l and f). Finally, a slight but not significant increase of TH-immunopositive cell density was observed in the SNpc when comparing vehicle- and JWH-018-treated mice (Mann-Whitney test: M-W U = 2.50, p > 0.05) (Fig. 7C, panels l and f).

The treatment was associated with the reduction of dopamine D₁ and

Fig. 7. Cerebral TH-immunostaining pattern in JWH-018 (6 mg/kg)-treated mice. Representative micrographs show TH immunolabeling in selected brain areas, i.e., primary motor cortex, hippocampus, striatum, and SNpc from both vehicle- (a–f) and JWH-018-treated mice (g–l). I–VI: cerebral cortex layers. CA: Cornu Ammonis and its subdivisions: CA1, CA2, CA3 and CA4; DG: Dentate Gyrus. Light microscopy magnification: 100 × (a, d, g and j; scale bars: 200 µm); 400 × (b, c, e, f, h, i, k and l; scale bars: 20 µm and 50 µm, for b, c, h, i and e, f, k, l, respectively). Histograms (A–C) illustrate the quantitative evaluation of TH-immunopositive cells OD in the striatum (A) as well as TH-immunopositive cells OD and density in the SNpc (B and C, respectively) of vehicle- (white bars) and JWH018-treated animals (black bars). *** $p < 0.001$. N. of sections: 20/animal.

D₂ receptors in the motor cortex (matrix cells), hippocampus, striatum, and cerebellum (Purkinje cells), as well as with an elevation in TH levels in the SNpc.

4. Discussion

This study evaluated for the first time the effects induced by repeated treatment with the synthetic cannabinoid (SC) agonist JWH-018 on spontaneous locomotor activity (open field test) and aggressive behavior (resident-intruder test) in mice, focusing on its potential impact on the dopaminergic system. The acute injection of SC reduced the motor activity and slightly increased aggressiveness in mice, while a progressive increase of distance travelled and bites inflicted by mice was observed at the following injections. Interestingly, the facilitation of spontaneous locomotion and aggressiveness observed in JWH-018-treated mice was accompanied by significant alterations in cortical, hippocampal, striatal and cerebellar expression levels of dopamine D₁ receptor, dopamine D₂ receptor and tyrosine hydroxylase (TH).

Although the first injection (day 1) of the synthetic cannabinoid reduced motor activity, a significant increase in the total distance travelled by mice was observed at day 3 and day 7. Both the motor inhibition (day 1) and facilitation (day 3 and day 7) have been prevented by pre-treatment with the cannabinoid CB₁ receptor preferring antagonist AM-251. The effect observed at day 1 is in line with the inhibition of motor activity induced by SCs via acting on CB₁ receptors (Corli et al., 2022; Tirri et al., 2022) located in the cerebellum and basal ganglia (Rodríguez de Fonseca et al., 1998; Morera-Herreras et al., 2012; Funada

et al., 2020). In fact, synthetic agonists of cannabinoid receptors can affect dopaminergic circuitries and central glutamatergic functions, thus influencing locomotor activity in rodents (Morera-Herreras et al., 2012; Funada et al., 2020). Further evidence confirming the psychostimulant properties of SCs has recently emerged as, in line with the present results, repeated treatment with JWH-018 (Bilel et al., 2023) or AKB-48 (Corli et al., 2024) was reported to facilitate spontaneous locomotion in mice.

Interestingly, also the pre-treatment with SCH23390 (dopamine D_{1/5} receptor antagonist) or haloperidol (dopamine D_{2/3} receptor antagonist), as well as the simultaneous blockade of dopamine D_{1/5} and D_{2/3} receptors, prevented the motor facilitation observed at day 7. Involvement of the dopaminergic system in JWH-induced motor effects is supported by our immunohistochemical data that revealed a region-specific downregulation of D₁ and D₂ dopamine receptors in the cortex, hippocampus, striatum, and cerebellum. These changes in receptor levels were paralleled by TH upregulation in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc), which suggests a boost in dopaminergic transmission/circuitry activity involving mesocortical and mesolimbic pathways. The role of dopaminergic D₁-like and D₂-like dopamine receptors in these brain areas has been established with reference to the control of movement (Panigrahi et al., 2015; Özkan et al., 2017; Bonnavion et al., 2024), suggesting that different downstream signaling pathways related to both G_{s/olf} and G_{i/o} proteins and with opposed effects on adenylyl cyclase, might be involved in the psychostimulant effects observed after exposure to JWH-018 (Ledonne and Mercuri, 2017). This is consistent with the potential functional interaction between the dopamine D₂ and

the cannabinoid CB₁ receptors, which are both highly expressed within the basal ganglia in rodents (Tsou et al., 1998). In fact, the indirect role of cannabinoid CB₁ receptors expressed in the striatal areas in modulating basal ganglia motor circuits has been described (Glass and Felder, 1997; van der Stelt and Di Marzo, 2003). Due to their localization, these receptors can influence the activity of both inhibitory- (Fitzgerald et al., 2012; Wallmichrath and Szabo, 2002) and excitatory-type (Gerdeman and Lovinger, 2001) synapses linked to midbrain dopaminergic neurons. As reviewed by Covey and colleagues, the suppression of the inhibitory input onto GABA receptors exerted by cannabinoids may result in enhanced dopaminergic neurotransmission (Covey et al., 2017). Indeed, intravenous administration of a cannabinoid CB₁ receptor agonist has been shown to increase the bursting activity of the dopaminergic neurons in the Ventral Tegmental Area (VTA) (Cheer et al., 2004), whose efferent fibers project to the NAc. Nonetheless, cannabinoid CB₁ receptors are widely expressed in the cerebellum, which in turn can modulate the activity of the striatum in the basal ganglia (Ichinohe et al., 2000; Hoshi et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2014). Moreover, the cerebellum has been suggested to facilitate the activity of dopamine in the striatum (Washburn et al., 2024), which seems to be closely related to the onset (Boecker et al., 2008; da Silva et al., 2018; Howe and Dombeck, 2016) and vigor (Palmiter, 2008; Panigrahi et al., 2015) of movement. Washburn and colleagues have shown that optogenetic activation of cerebellar axons in the substantia nigra can increase walking activity of mice (Washburn et al., 2024). Further studies have provided compelling evidence about the existence of dynamic and agonist-modulated D₂ and CB₁ receptors complexes. The simultaneous activation of dopamine D₂ and cannabinoid CB₁ receptors has been related to higher levels of the complex and its differential preference for signaling. The initial synergistic inhibitory effect induced by cannabinoid receptors agonists is replaced by the coupling to the alpha subunit of G_s protein and the stimulation of cAMP-dependent pathway (Kearn et al., 2005). Therefore, this data suggests the potential role of the activation of D₂/CB₁ receptors complexes in the progressive modulation of the response of dopaminergic pathways' neurons.

The repeated injection of JWH-018 progressively enhance aggressive response in mice. Yet, the present findings lead to hypothesize the involvement of sensitization mechanisms that favor both hyperactivity and territorial aggressive behavior. The pre-treatment with the antagonist AM-251 prevented the stimulated aggressiveness observed at day 1, day 3 and day 7. Similarly, the prior injection of SCH23390 (D_{1/5} antagonist) and haloperidol (D_{2/3} antagonist), as well as the simultaneous blockade of dopamine D_{1/5} and D_{2/3} receptors, prevent the proaggressive effect observed at day 7. Although low doses of cannabinoid receptor agonists have been shown to reduce aggressiveness (Cherek et al., 1980; Chang et al., 2021), high dosages of these compounds promote aggressive behaviors in mice and rats (Alves and Carlini, 1973; Bac et al., 1998; Canazza et al., 2016). In this context, increased aggressiveness has been observed in CB₁ receptors-knockout mice (Martin et al., 2002; Haller et al., 2004). In line with this, we found that the increase in the overall mean bites inflicted by the resident in the resident-intruder test performed at day 1 was lower than bites inflicted by the same mice at day 3 and day 7 of treatment. Repeated administration of SCs results in the decrease of cannabinoid CB₁ receptor levels in the CNS (Corli et al., 2024) and, in turn, the loss of cannabinoid receptor function has been suggested to lead to increased aggression (Migliaro et al., 2023). However, a significant inhibition of the distance travelled by mice in the open field test has been reported after the first injection of JWH-018, which could be related to the lower level of aggression observed in the same treatment paradigm.

To date, evidence demonstrating the relationship between aggression and the mesocortical and mesolimbic dopaminergic system has emerged (Golden et al., 2019; Ghosal et al., 2019; Beiderbeck et al., 2012). Motivational stimuli, i.e., the favorable probability of overpowering through aggression (Golden et al., 2019), can be linked to

increased dopamine levels in the NAc (Covey and Yocky, 2021). This is consistent with the increased NAc dopamine levels observed in rats after aggressively behaving (van Erp and Miczek, 2000). The firing of neurons in the NAc is influenced by excitatory glutamatergic input from different sites including the VTA (Covey and Yocky, 2021), which dopaminergic neurons projecting to the lateral septum have been shown to promote aggressiveness (Mahadevia et al., 2021). Thus, the activation of cannabinoid CB₁ receptors may mediate the aggressive response evoked by the repeated treatment with JWH-018 by acting on inhibitory (Wallmichrath and Szabo, 2002; Fitzgerald et al., 2012) or excitatory-type (Gerdeman and Lovinger, 2001) synapses linked to midbrain dopaminergic neurons.

Furthermore, the key role played by dopamine D1 and D2 receptors, expressed in specific areas involved in dopaminergic mesocortical and mesolimbic pathways (i.e., cortex, striatum, and hippocampus), in modulating stress response (e.g., aggressiveness) has been confirmed by scientific literature (Couppis and Kennedy, 2008; Frau et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023). A compelling study by Felipe and colleagues, for example, has pointed out reduced D1 expression in aggressive mice involved in social stress preclinical models (Felipe et al., 2021). Our immunohistochemical data show a dopamine D1 and D2 receptors decrease in brain cortex, hippocampus, striatum, but also in the cerebellar Purkinje neurons. Supporting these results, Cutando and colleagues have demonstrated that altered cerebellar dopamine D2 receptors levels, which are mainly expressed in Purkinje cell and regulate its synaptic efficacy, result in altered sociability and preference for social novelty without affecting motor activity (Cutando et al., 2022).

The dopamine D₁ and D₂ receptors downregulation is paralleled by TH upregulation. We may reasonably hypothesize that the enhanced activity of TH, crucially involved in catecholamine biosynthesis, and the consequent rise in dopamine expression levels, could lead to the internalization/degradation of both D₁ and D₂, due to their repeated activation (Bartlett et al., 2005; Jones-Tabah et al., 2022).

Therefore, taken as a whole, the present results support the hypothesis that psychomotor responses evoked by repeated treatment with SCs is likely linked to alterations in central dopaminergic circuits.

5. Conclusions

This study shows that repeated treatment with the synthetic cannabinoid JWH-018 (6 mg/kg, i.p.) progressively increases spontaneous locomotor activity and aggressive behavior in mice, via CB₁ receptors mediated- and dopamine-dependent mechanisms. In translational paradigm, it suggests the great issue related to the use of synthetic cannabinoids, especially in relation to the effective management of intoxications and awareness of potential consumers with reference to the atypical psychostimulant effects of these substances.

Despite the epidemiological proof of a higher risk of abuse (ESPAD, 2019) and intoxications (Bush and Woodwell, 2014; Pelletti et al., 2022) for males, the use of one sex only remains a limitation of this study. In light of previous clinical (Spindle et al., 2021) and preclinical (Fattore et al., 2007, 2010; Corli et al., 2024) findings, future research is needed to clarify the role of sex in the long-term effects induced by prolonged exposure to synthetic cannabinoids.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giorgia Corli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fabrizio De Luca:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sabrina Biele:** Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marta Bassi:** Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Elisa Roda:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Paola Rossi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Liana Fattore:**

Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Carlo Alessandro Locatelli:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Matteo Marti:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Ethical statements

All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed. All procedures performed in the studies involving animals were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institution or practice at which the studies were conducted. The Project was initiated in collaboration with the Presidency of the Council of Ministers-DPA Anti-Drug Policies (Italy).

Data statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Declaration of Competing interest

Declarations of interest: none.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Alipour, A., Patel, P.B., Shabbir, Z., Gabrielson, S., 2019. Review of the many faces of synthetic cannabinoid toxicities. *Ment. Health Clin.* 9 (2), 93–99. <https://doi.org/10.9740/mhc.2019.03.093>.
- Alves, C.N., Carlini, E.A., 1973. Effects of acute and chronic administration of Cannabis sativa extract on the mouse-killing behavior of rats. *Life sciences* 13 (1), 75–85. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3205\(73\)90279-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3205(73)90279-8).
- Andersen, H.K., Walsh, K.B., 2021. Molecular signaling of synthetic cannabinoids: Comparison of CB1 receptor and TRPV1 channel activation. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 907, 174301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2021.174301>.
- Asano, Y., Sasaki, D., Ikoma, Y., Matsui, K., 2024. Glial tone of aggression. *Neurosci. Res.* 202, 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neures.2023.11.008>.
- Bac, P., Pages, N., Herrenknecht, C., Paris, M., 1998. Measurement of the three phases of muricidal behavior induced by delta9-tetrahydrocannabinol in isolated, fasting rats. *Physiol. Behav.* 63 (5), 815–820. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-9384\(97\)00543-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-9384(97)00543-x).
- Bartlett, S.E., Enquist, J., Hopf, F.W., Lee, J.H., Gladher, F., Kharazia, V., Waldhoer, M., Mailliard, W.S., Armstrong, R., Bonci, A., Whistler, J.L., 2005. Dopamine responsiveness is regulated by targeted sorting of D2 receptors. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 102 (32), 11521–11526. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0502418102>.
- Bassir Nia, A., Mann, C.L., Spriggs, S., DeFrancisco, D.R., Carbonaro, S., Parvez, L., Galyner, I.I., Perkel, C.A., Hurd, Y.L., 2019. The relevance of sex in the association of synthetic cannabinoid use with psychosis and agitation in an inpatient population. *J. Clin. Psychiatr.* 80 (4), 18m12539. <https://doi.org/10.4088/JCP.18m12539>.
- Beiderbeck, D.I., Reber, S.O., Havasi, A., Bredewold, R., Veenema, A.H., Neumann, I.D., 2012. High and abnormal forms of aggression in rats with extremes in trait anxiety–involvement of the dopamine system in the nucleus accumbens. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* 37 (12), 1969–1980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2012.04.011>.
- Bilel, S., Tirri, M., Arfè, R., Ossato, A., Trapella, C., Serpelloni, G., Neri, M., Fattore, L., Marti, M., 2020. Novel halogenated synthetic cannabinoids impair sensorimotor functions in mice. *Neurotoxicology* 76, 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2019.10.002>.
- Bilel, S., Zamberletti, E., Caffino, L., Tirri, M., Mottarlini, F., Arfè, R., Barbieri, M., Beggiato, S., Boccuto, F., Bernardi, T., Casati, S., Brini, A.T., Parolaro, D., Rubino, T., Ferraro, L., Vimagalli, F., Marti, M., 2023. Cognitive dysfunction and impaired neuroplasticity following repeated exposure to the synthetic cannabinoid JWH-018 in male mice. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 180 (21), 2777–2801. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bph.16164>.
- Boecker, H., Jankowski, J., Ditter, P., Scheef, L., 2008. A role of the basal ganglia and midbrain nuclei for initiation of motor sequences. *Neuroimage* 39 (3), 1356–1369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2007.09.069>.
- Bonnaïon, P., Varin, C., Fakhouri, G., Martínez Olondo, P., De Groot, A., Cornil, A., Lorenzo Lopez, R., Pozuelo Fernandez, E., Isingrini, E., Rainer, Q., Xu, K., Tzavara, E., Vigneault, E., Dumas, S., de Kerchove d’Exaerde, A., Giros, B., 2024. Striatal projection neurons coexpressing dopamine D1 and D2 receptors modulate the motor function of D1- and D2-SPNs. *Nat. Neurosci.* 27 (9), 1783–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-024-01694-4>.
- Bush, D.M., Woodwell, D.A., 2014. Update: Drug-Related emergency department visits involving synthetic cannabinoids. In: *The CBHSQ Report*, pp. 1–10. Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (US).
- Canazza, I., Ossato, A., Trapella, C., Fantinati, A., De Luca, M.A., Margiani, G., Vincenzi, F., Rimondo, C., Di Rosa, F., Gregori, A., Varani, K., Borea, P.A., Serpelloni, G., Marti, M., 2016. Effect of the novel synthetic cannabinoids AKB48 and 5F-AKB48 on “tetrad”, sensorimotor, neurological and neurochemical responses in mice. In vitro and in vivo pharmacological studies. *Psychopharmacology* 233 (21–22), 3685–3709. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-016-4402-y>.
- Chang, C.H., Liu, Y.C., Sun, C.Y., Su, C.L., Gean, P.W., 2021. Regulation of stress-provoked aggressive behavior using endocannabinoids. *Neurobiology of stress* 15, 100337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ynstr.2021.100337>.
- Cheer, J.F., Wassum, K.M., Heien, M.L., Phillips, P.E., Wightman, R.M., 2004. Cannabinoids enhance subsecond dopamine release in the nucleus accumbens of awake rats. *J. Neurosci.* : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience 24 (18), 4393–4400. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0529-04.2004>.
- Chen, C.H., Fremont, R., Arteaga-Bracho, E.E., Khodakhah, K., 2014. Short latency cerebellar modulation of the basal ganglia. *Nat. Neurosci.* 17 (12), 1767–1775. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3868>.
- Cherek, D.R., Thompson, T., Kelly, T., 1980. Chronic delta 9-tetrahydrocannabinol administration and schedule-induced aggression. *Pharmacology, biochemistry, and behavior* 12 (2), 305–309. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0091-3057\(80\)90374-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0091-3057(80)90374-3).
- Cizkova, K., Foltynkova, T., Gachechiladze, M., Tauber, Z., 2021. Comparative analysis of immunohistochemical staining intensity determined by light microscopy, ImageJ and QuPath in placental hofbauer cells. *Acta Histochem. Cytoc.* 54 (1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1267/ahc.20-00032>.
- Cohen, J., 1988. *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*, second ed. Lawrence Erlbaum, Hillsdale, NJ.
- Corli, G., Roda, E., Tirri, M., Bilel, S., De Luca, F., Strano-Rossi, S., Gaudio, R.M., De-Giorgio, F., Fattore, L., Locatelli, C.A., Marti, M., 2024. Sex-specific behavioural, metabolic, and immunohistochemical changes after repeated administration of the synthetic cannabinoid AKB48 in mice. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 181 (9), 1361–1382. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bph.16311>.
- Corli, G., Tirri, M., Arfè, R., Bilel, S., Marchetti, B., Gregori, A., Di Rosa, F., Vincenzi, F., De-Giorgio, F., Borea, P.A., Varani, K., Marti, M., 2022. Behavioral and binding studies on the quinolinyl ester indoles 5F-PB22 (5F-QUPIIC) and BB-22 (QUCHIC) in the mouse model. *Emerging Trends in Drugs, Addictions, and Health* 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etedah.2022.100039>.
- Corli, G., Tirri, M., Bilel, S., Arfè, R., Coccini, T., Roda, E., Marchetti, B., Vincenzi, F., Zauli, G., Borea, P.A., Locatelli, C.A., Varani, K., Marti, M., 2023. MAM-2201 acute administration impairs motor, sensorimotor, prepulse inhibition, and memory functions in mice: a comparison with its analogue AM-2201. *Psychopharmacology* 240 (7), 1435–1452. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-023-06378-8>.
- Couppis, M.H., Kennedy, C.H., 2008. The rewarding effect of aggression is reduced by nucleus accumbens dopamine receptor antagonism in mice. *Psychopharmacology* 197 (3), 449–456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-007-1054-y>.
- Covey, D.P., Mateo, Y., Sulzer, D., Cheer, J.F., Lovinger, D.M., 2017. Endocannabinoid modulation of dopamine neurotransmission. *Neuropharmacology* 124, 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2017.04.033>.
- Covey, D.P., Yocky, A.G., 2021. Endocannabinoid modulation of Nucleus accumbens microcircuitry and terminal dopamine release. *Front. Synaptic Neurosci.* 13, 734975. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsyn.2021.734975>.
- Cutando, L., Puighermanal, E., Castell, L., Tarot, P., Belle, M., Bertaso, F., Arango-Lievano, M., Ango, F., Rubinstein, M., Quintana, A., Chédotal, A., Mameli, M., Valjent, E., 2022. Cerebellar dopamine D2 receptors regulate social behaviors. *Nat. Neurosci.* 25 (7), 900–911. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-022-01092-8>.

- da Silva, J.A., Tecuapetla, F., Paixão, V., Costa, R.M., 2018. Dopamine neuron activity before action initiation gates and invigorates future movements. *Nature* 554 (7691), 244–248. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25457>.
- De Luca, F., Roda, E., Ratto, D., Desiderio, A., Venuti, M.T., Ramieri, M., Bottone, M.G., Savino, E., Rossi, P., 2023. Fighting secondary triple-negative breast cancer in cerebellum: a powerful aid from a medicinal mushrooms blend. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedicine & pharmacotherapie* 159, 114262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2023.114262>.
- de Oliveira, M.C., Vides, M.C., Lassi, D.L.S., Torales, J., Ventriglio, A., Bombana, H.S., Leyton, V., Périco, C.A., Negrão, A.B., Malbergier, A., Castaldelli-Maia, J.M., 2023. Toxicity of synthetic cannabinoids in K2/Spice: a systematic review. *Brain Sci.* 13 (7), 990. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci13070990>.
- De-Giorgio, F., Bergamin, E., Bilel, S., Tirri, M., Arfè, R., Marchetti, B., Corli, G., Serpelloni, G., Marti, M., 2021. Ethanol enhanced MDPV- and cocaine-induced aggressive behavior in mice: forensic implications. *Drug Alcohol Depend.* 229 (Pt A), 109125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2021.109125>.
- ESPAD, 2019. ESPAD report 2019. <http://espad.org/espad-report-2019>.
- EUDA, 2017. Synthetic cannabinoids in Europe. <https://www.euda.europa.eu/topics/pods/synthetic-cannabinoids.en>.
- EUDA, 2023. European drug report 2023: trends and developments. <https://www.emcdda.europa.eu/publications/european-drug-report/2023.en>.
- Fattore, L., Spano, M.S., Altea, S., Angius, F., Fadda, P., Fratta, W., 2007. Cannabinoid self-administration in rats: sex differences and the influence of ovarian function. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 152 (5), 795–804. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bjp.0707465>.
- Fattore, L., Spano, M.S., Altea, S., Fadda, P., Fratta, W., 2010. Drug- and cue-induced reinstatement of cannabinoid-seeking behaviour in male and female rats: influence of ovarian hormones. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* 160 (3), 724–735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.2010.00734.x>.
- Felippe, R.M., Oliveira, G.M., Barbosa, R.S., Esteves, B.D., Gonzaga, B.M.S., Horita, S.I. M., Garzoni, L.R., Beghini, D.G., Araújo-Jorge, T.C., Frago, V.M.S., 2021. Experimental social stress: Dopaminergic receptors, oxidative stress, and c-Fos protein are involved in highly aggressive behavior. *Front. Cell. Neurosci.* 15, 696834. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2021.696834>.
- Ferrari, P.F., van Erp, A.M., Tornatzky, W., Miczek, K.A., 2003. Accumbal dopamine and serotonin in anticipation of the next aggressive episode in rats. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 17 (2), 371–378. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1460-9568.2003.02447.x>.
- Fitzgerald, M.L., Shobin, E., Pickel, V.M., 2012. Cannabinoid modulation of the dopaminergic circuitry: implications for limbic and striatal output. *Progress in neuro-psychopharmacology & biological psychiatry* 38 (1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpb.2011.12.004>.
- Foti, F., Bilel, S., Tirri, M., Arfè, R., Boccuto, F., Bernardi, T., Serpelloni, G., De-Giorgio, F., Marti, M., 2021. Low-normal doses of methiopropamine induce aggressive behaviour in mice. *Psychopharmacology* 238 (7), 1847–1856. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-021-05813-y>.
- Frau, R., Fanni, S., Serra, V., Simola, N., Godar, S.C., Traccis, F., Devoto, P., Bortolato, M., Melis, M., 2019. Dysfunctional mesocortical dopamine circuit at pre-adolescence is associated to aggressive behavior in MAO-A hypomorphic mice exposed to early life stress. *Neuropharmacology* 159, 107517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2019.01.032>.
- Freund, S.A., Banning, A.S., 2017. Synthetic cannabinoids: a review of the clinical implications of a new drug of choice. *JAAPA : Off. J. Am. Acad. Physician Assistants (JAAPA)* 30 (11), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.JAA.0000525914.28344.e2>.
- Funada, M., Takebayashi-Ohsawa, M., Tomiyama, K.I., 2020. Synthetic cannabinoids enhanced ethanol-induced motor impairments through reduction of central glutamate neurotransmission. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 408, 115283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2020.115283>.
- Gerdeman, G., Lovinger, D.M., 2001. CB1 cannabinoid receptor inhibits synaptic release of glutamate in rat dorsolateral striatum. *Journal of neurophysiology* 85 (1), 468–471. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.2001.85.1.468>.
- Ghosal, S., Sandi, C., van der Kooij, M.A., 2019. Neuropharmacology of the mesolimbic system and associated circuits on social hierarchies. *Neuropharmacology* 159, 107498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2019.01.013>.
- Glass, M., Felder, C.C., 1997. Concurrent stimulation of cannabinoid CB1 and dopamine D2 receptors augments cAMP accumulation in striatal neurons: evidence for a Gs linkage to the CB1 receptor. *J. Neurosci. : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience* 17 (14), 5327–5333. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.17-14-05327.1997>.
- Golden, S.A., Jin, M., Shaham, Y., 2019. Animal models of (or for) aggression reward, addiction, and relapse: behavior and circuits. *J. Neurosci. : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience* 39 (21), 3996–4008. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0151-19.2019>.
- Graddy, R., Buresh, M.E., Rastegar, D.A., 2018. New and emerging illicit psychoactive substances. *Med. Clin.* 102 (4), 697–714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcna.2018.02.010>.
- Haller, J., Varga, B., Ledent, C., Barna, I., Freund, T.F., 2004. Context-dependent effects of CB1 cannabinoid gene disruption on anxiety-like and social behaviour in mice. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 19 (7), 1906–1912. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2004.03293.x>.
- Hoshi, E., Tremblay, L., Féger, J., Carras, P.L., Strick, P.L., 2005. The cerebellum communicates with the basal ganglia. *Nat. Neurosci.* 8 (11), 1491–1493. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1544>.
- Howe, M.W., Dombeck, D.A., 2016. Rapid signalling in distinct dopaminergic axons during locomotion and reward. *Nature* 535 (7613), 505–510. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature18942>.
- Ichinohe, N., Mori, F., Shoumura, K., 2000. A di-synaptic projection from the lateral cerebellar nucleus to the laterodorsal part of the striatum via the central lateral nucleus of the thalamus in the rat. *Brain Res.* 880 (1–2), 191–197. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-8993\(00\)02744-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-8993(00)02744-x).
- Jackman, S.L., Chen, C.H., Offermann, H.L., Drew, I.R., Harrison, B.M., Bowman, A.M., Flick, K.M., Flaquer, I., Regehr, W.G., 2020. Cerebellar purkinje cell activity modulates aggressive behavior. *Elife* 9, e53229. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53229>.
- Jones-Tabah, J., Mohammad, H., Paulus, E.G., Clarke, P.B.S., Hébert, T.E., 2022. The signaling and pharmacology of the dopamine D1 receptor. *Front. Cell. Neurosci.* 15, 806618. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2021.806618>.
- Kearn, C.S., Blake-Palmer, K., Daniel, E., Mackie, K., Glass, M., 2005. Concurrent stimulation of cannabinoid CB1 and dopamine D2 receptors enhances heterodimer formation: a mechanism for receptor cross-talk? *Mol. Pharmacol.* 67 (5), 1697–1704. <https://doi.org/10.1124/mol.104.006882>.
- Klein, M.O., Battagello, D.S., Cardoso, A.R., Hauser, D.N., Bittencourt, J.C., Correa, R.G., 2019. Dopamine: functions, signaling, and association with neurological diseases. *Cell. Mol. Neurobiol.* 39 (1), 31–59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10571-018-0632-3>.
- Kwiatkowski, C.C., Akaeze, H., Ndebe, I., Goodwin, N., Eagle, A.L., Moon, K., Bender, A. R., Golden, S.A., Robison, A.J., 2021. Quantitative standardization of resident mouse behavior for studies of aggression and social defeat. *Neuropsychopharmacology : official publication of the American College of Neuropsychopharmacology* 46 (9), 1584–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-021-01018-1>.
- Ledonne, A., Mercuri, N.B., 2017. Current concepts on the neuropathological relevance of dopaminergic receptors. *Front. Cell. Neurosci.* 11, 27. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2017.00027>.
- Luethi, D., Liechti, M.E., 2020. Designer drugs: mechanism of action and adverse effects. *Arch. Toxicol.* 94 (4), 1085–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-020-02693-7>.
- Mahadevia, D., Saha, R., Manganaro, A., Chuhma, N., Ziolkowski-Blake, A., Morgan, A. A., Dumitriu, D., Rayport, S., Ansorge, M.S., 2021. Dopamine promotes aggression in mice via ventral tegmental area to lateral septum projections. *Nat. Commun.* 12 (1), 6796. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27092-z>.
- Martin, M., Ledent, C., Parmentier, M., Maldonado, R., Valverde, O., 2002. Involvement of CB1 cannabinoid receptors in emotional behaviour. *Psychopharmacology* 159 (4), 379–387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-001-0946-5>.
- Migliaro, M., Ruiz-Contreras, A.E., Herrera-Solís, A., Méndez-Díaz, M., Prospéro-García, O.E., 2023. Endocannabinoid system and aggression across animal species. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 153, 105375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2023.105375>.
- Miller, A.E., Daiwile, A.P., Cadet, J.L., 2022. Sex-dependent alterations in the mRNA expression of enzymes involved in dopamine synthesis and breakdown after methamphetamine self-administration. *Neurotox. Res.* 40 (5), 1464–1478. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12640-022-00545-z>.
- Morera-Herreras, T., Miguelez, C., Aristieta, A., Ruiz-Ortega, J.Á., Ugedo, L., 2012. Endocannabinoid modulation of dopaminergic motor circuits. *Front. Pharmacol.* 3, 110. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2012.00110>.
- Ossato, A., Uccelli, L., Bilel, S., Canazza, I., Di Domenico, G., Pasquali, M., Pupillo, G., De Luca, M.A., Boschi, A., Vincenzi, F., Rimondo, C., Beggiano, S., Ferraro, L., Varani, K., Borea, P.A., Serpelloni, G., De-Giorgio, F., Marti, M., 2017. Psychostimulant effect of the synthetic cannabinoid JWH-018 and AKB48: behavioral, neurochemical, and dopamine transporter scan imaging studies in mice. *Front. Psychiatr.* 8, 130. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2017.00130>.
- Ossato, A., Vigolo, A., Trapella, C., Seri, C., Rimondo, C., Serpelloni, G., Marti, M., 2015. JWH-018 impairs sensorimotor functions in mice. *Neuroscience* 300, 174–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2015.05.021>.
- Özkan, M., Johnson, N.W., Sehrlir, U.S., Woodhall, G.L., Stanford, I.M., 2017. Dopamine acting at D1-like, D2-like and α 1-adrenergic receptors differentially modulates theta and gamma oscillatory activity in primary motor cortex. *PLoS One* 12 (7), e0181633. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0181633>.
- Palmiter, R.D., 2008. Dopamine signaling in the dorsal striatum is essential for motivated behaviors: lessons from dopamine-deficient mice. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1129, 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1417.003>.
- Panigrahi, B., Martin, K.A., Li, Y., Graves, A.R., Vollmer, A., Olson, L., Mensh, B.D., Karpova, A.Y., Dudman, J.T., 2015. Dopamine is required for the neural representation and control of movement vigor. *Cell* 162 (6), 1418–1430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.08.014>.
- Pelletti, G., Boscolo-Berto, R., Barone, R., Giorgetti, A., Fiorentini, C., Pascali, J.P., Fais, P., Pelotti, S., 2022. Gender differences in driving under the influence of psychoactive drugs: evidence mapping of real case studies and meta-analysis. *Forensic Sci. Int.* 341, 111479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2022.111479>.
- Roda, E., De Luca, F., Ratto, D., Priori, E.C., Savino, E., Bottone, M.G., Rossi, P., 2023. Cognitive healthy aging in mice: boosting memory by an ergothioneine-rich *Hericium erinaceus* primordium extract. *Biology* 12 (2), 196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12020196>.
- Roda, E., Luca, F., Locatelli, C.A., Ratto, D., Di Iorio, C., Savino, E., Bottone, M.G., Rossi, P., 2020. From a medicinal mushroom blend a direct anticancer effect on triple-negative breast cancer: a preclinical study on lung metastases. *Molecules* 25 (22), 5400. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225400>.
- Roda, E., Priori, E.C., Ratto, D., De Luca, F., Di Iorio, C., Angelone, P., Locatelli, C.A., Desiderio, A., Goppa, L., Savino, E., Bottone, M.G., Rossi, P., 2021. Neuroprotective metabolites of *Hericium erinaceus* promote neuro-healthy aging. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 22 (12), 6379. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22126379>.
- Rodríguez de Fonseca, F., Del Arco, I., Martín-Calderón, J.L., Gorriti, M.A., Navarro, M., 1998. Role of the endogenous cannabinoid system in the regulation of motor activity. *Neurobiol. Dis.* 5 (6 Pt B), 483–501. <https://doi.org/10.1006/nbdi.1998.0217>.
- Rojek, S., Klys, M., Maciów-Głąb, M., Kula, K., 2017. A new challenge in forensic toxicology exemplified by a case of murder under the influence of a synthetic

- cannabinoid - AM-2201. *Legal medicine* (Tokyo, Japan) 27, 25–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.legalmed.2017.06.004>.
- Roque-Bravo, R., Silva, R.S., Malheiro, R.F., Carmo, H., Carvalho, F., da Silva, D.D., Silva, J.P., 2023. Synthetic cannabinoids: a pharmacological and toxicological overview. *Annu. Rev. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* 63, 187–209. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-031122-113758>.
- Schwartz, M.D., Trecki, J., Edison, L.A., Steck, A.R., Arnold, J.K., Gerona, R.R., 2015. A common source outbreak of severe delirium associated with exposure to the novel synthetic cannabinoid ADB-PINACA. *J. Emerg. Med.* 48 (5), 573–580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemermed.2014.12.038>.
- Spindle, T.R., Martin, E.L., Grabenauer, M., Woodward, T., Milburn, M.A., Vandrey, R., 2021. Assessment of cognitive and psychomotor impairment, subjective effects, and blood THC concentrations following acute administration of oral and vaporized cannabis. *J. Psychopharmacol.* 35 (7), 786–803. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02698811211021583>.
- Takahashi, A., Quadros, I.M., de Almeida, R.M., Miczek, K.A., 2012. Behavioral and pharmacogenetics of aggressive behavior. *Current topics in behavioral neurosciences* 12, 73–138. https://doi.org/10.1007/7854_2011_191.
- Tielbeek, J.J., Al-Itejawi, Z., Zijlmans, J., Polderman, T.J., Buckholtz, J.W., Popma, A., 2018. The impact of chronic stress during adolescence on the development of aggressive behavior: a systematic review on the role of the dopaminergic system in rodents. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 91, 187–197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2016.10.009>.
- Tirri, M., Arfè, R., Bilel, S., Corli, G., Marchetti, B., Fantinati, A., Vincenzi, F., De-Giorgio, F., Camuto, C., Mazzarino, M., Barbieri, M., Gaudio, R.M., Varani, K., Borea, P.A., Botrè, F., Marti, M., 2022. In vivo bio-activation of JWH-175 to JWH-018: pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic studies in mice. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 23 (14), 8030. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23148030>.
- Tsou, K., Brown, S., Sañudo-Peña, M.C., Mackie, K., Walker, J.M., 1998. Immunohistochemical distribution of cannabinoid CB1 receptors in the rat central nervous system. *Neuroscience* 83 (2), 393–411. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522\(97\)00436-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522(97)00436-3).
- van der Stelt, M., Di Marzo, V., 2003. The endocannabinoid system in the basal ganglia and in the mesolimbic reward system: implications for neurological and psychiatric disorders. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 480 (1–3), 133–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2003.08.101>.
- van Erp, A.M., Miczek, K.A., 2000. Aggressive behavior, increased accumbal dopamine, and decreased cortical serotonin in rats. *J. Neurosci. : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience* 20 (24), 9320–9325. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.20-24-09320.2000>.
- Vigolo, A., Ossato, A., Trapella, C., Vincenzi, F., Rimondo, C., Seri, C., Varani, K., Serpelloni, G., Marti, M., 2015. Novel halogenated derivatives of JWH-018: behavioral and binding studies in mice. *Neuropharmacology* 95, 68–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2015.02.008>.
- Wallmichrath, I., Szabo, B., 2002. Cannabinoids inhibit striatonigral GABAergic neurotransmission in the mouse. *Neuroscience* 113 (3), 671–682. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522\(02\)00109-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0306-4522(02)00109-4).
- Wang, C., Zhu, L., Zheng, W., Peng, H., Wang, J., Cui, Y., Liu, B., Jiang, T., 2023. Effects of childhood trauma on aggressive behaviors and hippocampal function: the modulation of COMT haplotypes. *Psychoradiology* 3, kkad013. <https://doi.org/10.1093/psyrad/kkad013>.
- Washburn, S., Oñate, M., Yoshida, J., Vera, J., Bhuvanandaram, R., Khatami, L., Nadim, F., Khodakhah, K., 2024. The cerebellum directly modulates the substantia nigra dopaminergic activity. *Nat. Neurosci.* 27 (3), 497–513. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-023-01560-9>.
- White, C.M., 2017. The pharmacologic and clinical effects of illicit synthetic cannabinoids. *J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 57 (3), 297–304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcph.827>.